

A Synchronization of Measurement and Instrumentation between Vedic and Modern Period

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Abstract:

In this paper, an intense and precise approach has been adopted by the authors to enlighten ancient measurement systems of weight, time, distance, spectrum of light, colour, speed of light, and some other parameters that have an important and valuable role in our day to day behaviour. Further a small effort has been made to link the current measurement systems with the primitive (of Vedic era) Indian measurement systems. This paper explains the concept of Vedic period measurement technology, and it's simple and suitable measuring instruments which was very adorable in India and as well as globally. These measurement systems were delightfully appreciated due to its simplicity, accuracy, and universality in nature. Along with this, some discussions in the modern CGS and MKS systems have also been sprinkled out for better understanding in both of the Vedic and modern measurement techniques. The authors also want to state the technologies in the Vedic period which was so advanced in the field of measurements such as the speed of sunlight was calculated, sunlight is the combination of seven colours was mentioned, number of planets which represent a day already told and many more. At the end of this paper, a short and pointed discussion has been made to lightening the amazing connection between Vedic time instruments and modern time electronic-based instruments. Vedic period instruments have the least side effects on atmosphere, environment, and mankind where the modern instruments only focus on its goal, and not on its side impaction.

Keywords: Yogana, Nimesa, Brahmastra, Pashupatastra, Rishi Agastya, Atharvaveda, Rig Veda, Brahmagupta, Aryabhata, Sushruta Samhita, Chitragupta.

1. INTRODUCTION

Measurement is an inevitable need of our day to day life. Without measurement, not a single work can be performed for daily survival. This system of measuring things is not a new one but as old as human civilization. Here one thing would be noticeable that only a few of this measurement process can able to put a milestone in the trading world of business and this is non-other than the Indian Vedic measurement system. Indian ancient measurement technique was one of the most easiest and less error based systems in this world [1]. During the time of the Vedic period, Indian measurement was established globally and accepted by many people in the world. This is still now adorable by every nation worldwide. It provides an easy, tricky, and simple procedure for various measuring parameters such as length, mass, weight, sound, colour, time, distance, and many more essential objects' measurements. Though in the current measurement system, a lot of changes have occurred, but still, Indian Vedic measurement systems don't lose their uniqueness and specialty even in this heavily competitive world [2]. The role of instruments in the Vedic period is highly advanced, nature-oriented, and highly related to modern instruments used in different areas.

In today's technological world, a new area of research has been introduced in the field of engineering, called Vedic engineering which is based on Indian Vedic knowledge. So before discussing the Indian Vedic measurement system and instruments, some points may be noted here on Vedic engineering.

2. VEDIC ENGINEERING

Veda which was written thousands of years ago deals with the branch of science and technology, concerned with the design, measurements, building, and use of different instruments and structures are called Vedic Engineering. The basis for any scientific discoveries and inventions is to explore, observe, experiment, and interpret. So in this context, Veda plays a much important role. Ancient Rishis proved the numerous scientific theories which were implemented later by modern scientists. Vedic period concept of engineering is more advanced and technology-oriented than the rest of the world at that time. In Vedic literature, there are so many verses that explain the hypothesis of the universe, biomedical instruments, life sciences, electronic-based instruments, astrology, metallurgy, chemistry, telegraphy, measurements, and Engineering. The world will remain always grateful towards those distinguished, renowned, and great Rishis who founded a root of knowledge in the shape of Vedas & Upanishads and scattered their expertise in the world without keeping any selfishness and expectations [3, 4]. Rig Veda discusses planets, electromagnetic effects, mass, and energy conservation. Rig Veda gives so many principles of science & engineering. Atharva Veda discussed electricity generation, spacecraft, measurement of colours, and many more. Ayurveda concerns about medicine, health issues, biomedical instrumentation, and many more things that are essential for the living organism. Sthapatya explains about architecture. In this paper, an attempt has been made to explain clearly about Indian Vedic measurement system, and Electronics & instrumentation engineering related to Vedic time.

3. MEASUREMENT IN VEDIC PERIOD

In India, various units of measurement are used during the Vedic period for calculations of length, time, mass, color, etc. for the social and religious events. During this Vedic period, the intrinsic measurement standards produced by many civilizations and emperors were widely accepted throughout their nation. Some important concepts can be briefly discussed further to understand the excellent measurement systems and unbelievable finest techniques that were discovered by the Indian Rishis and Munis [5].

3.1 Length Measurements in different periods

One can consider length as the most important measuring parameter of each step of the life. In the earlier measuring techniques, the main parameters used for length measurements were totally dependent on human body organs such as hands, length, and width of fingers, thumbs, body spans, and cubits as shown in Fig.1. But due to the variation in the size of the body organs from person to person, another substitution of using a piece of a stick of wood or other fabric as a unit of length gained the popularity of brilliant concepts in length measurements. In ancient India, dhanush (bow), the krosha andyojana were utilized as the unit of length [6].

Fig.1: Length measurement by different body parts

In Mughal emperor, Akbar period of rule, the gaj was widely used as a unit of length until the system of weights and measures was introduced in 1956. Every gaj was divided into twenty-four equal parts and each equal part was known as tassuj. The size of the bricks all over the area was the same during the Mohenjo- daro era (3000 B.C). The length, breadth, and width of bricks were invariably within the quantitative relation of 4:2:1 and could be considered as a standard value. In Arthashastra, Chanakya mentioned 2 kinds of dhanushas as a unit for lengths, and distances measurements; one was the ordinary dhanush, consisting of ninety-six angulas, and the other dhanusha was mentioned as garhpatya Dhanush which consists of 108 angulas, used for roads and distances measurements. The British period used foot and yard for measuring length. At that time, parmanu was the smallest unit of length. The ancient measurement system's element and the unit length definition with conversion may be written as [7]

- I. 8 parmanu=1 rajahkan (dust particle coming from the wheel of a chariot)
- II. 8 rajahkan = 1 liksha (egg of lice)
- III. 8 liksha = 1 yookamadhya
- IV. 8 yookamadhya = 1 yavamadhya
- V. 8 yuvamadhya = 1 angul (approximate width of a finger) = 2 cm = 0. 787402 inch
- VI. 8 angul=1 dhanurmushti=16cm=6. 299 inch
- VII. angul=1 dhanugraha= 8 cm = 3. 14961 inch
- VIII. 12 angul= 1 vitasti = 24 cm = 9. 44882 inch
- IX. 2 vitasti =1 aratni or hast (or haath) = 48 cm = 18. 8976 inch
- X. aratni (haath) = 1 dand or dhanush = 192 cm = 6. 299 feet
- XI. 10 dand=1 rajju=19. 2 meter =62. 9921 sq. ft
- XII. 2 rajju = 1 paridesh = 125. 98 feet
- XIII. 2000 dhanush = 1 krosh = 4199. 475 yard= 3840 meter (approx) = 3. 84 km
- XIV. Krosh (goruta) = 1 yojan \approx 9miles \approx 15km(approx.)

The Mughal measurement system was used to measure the length and land in terms of gaj and beegha with the following relationship [7].

- i. 1 girah= width of 3 fingers (Anguli)
- ii. 1 hath = 8 girah
- iii. 1 gaj = 2 hath
- iv. 1 kathi = 55/6 hath
- v. 1 pand = 20 kathi
- vi. 1 beegha = 20 pand
- vii. 1 beegha = 20 vishwa
- viii. 1 viswah = 20 viswansah.

In June 1864, the government of India recommended inch, foot, yard and mile for linear measurement and acre for area measurement with their conversion given as [7]:-

- i. 1 mile = 8 furlongs =1760 yards=1. 61 km
- ii. 1 furlong = 220 yards
- iii. 1 acre = 4840 sq. yards = 1/10
- iv. 1 sq. Yard = 9 sq. ft.
- v. 1 sq. mile = 640 acres
- vi. 1 hectare \approx 2.47 acres = 10000 sq. m. (approx.)

A committee was appointed on 10th October 1913 to recommend a system based on the combination of Indian & British systems. The two measuring units named "mile" and "furlong" were common markers on road in India in 1950. One inch was the minimum unit of length. Other linear

and land measures and their conversion may be given as [6]

- 1) 1 inch=2. 54 cm
- 2) 1 foot = 12 inch=30. 48 cm
- 3) 1 yard = 3 feet = 0. 0914metre
- 4) 1 furlong = 660 feet =220 yard
- 5) 1 mile = 1760 yards or 5280feet=1. 61 km
- 6) 1 chain = 22 yard
- 7) 1 acre = 43560 sq. feet = 4840 sq. yards
- 8) 1 sq. yard = 9 sq. ft.
- 9) 1 sq. meter = 1. 196 square gaj
- 10) 1 sq. gaj = 0. 836126 sq. meter
- 11) 1 kaththa \approx 2. 5 decimal = 1361. 25 sq. ft. \approx 100 sq. meter
- 12) 1 beegha = 2304. 576036 sq. meter
- 13) 1 sq. Mile \approx 2. 5 sq. km = 640acre

After the independence of India, it was a need for determining a modern measurement standard to ensure universe application and to avoid conflicts and ambiguity which were common in then measurement system. So the government established a measurement standard laboratory named the National Physical Laboratory (NPL) to introduce the metric system in India. The standards which maintained at NPL were compared periodically with the standards maintained at other so many international levels National Metrological Institutes as well as with the standard maintained at the BIPM, Paris [8]. This process confirms the very near equivalency of Indian national standards to those best laboratories of the rest of the world.

3.1.1 Comparison between Vedic and modern technique of length measurement

Earlier the length or distance was measured in many ways such as angul, arm length, and foot length. In the Now, the similarities among the methods of both the ages (Vedas and modern times) lie in the calibration. Earlier in Vedic time, the reference was the methods such as the angul, arm, and foot length [9] whereas now these have been a simple scale, Vernier Calipers, and screw gauge. The Vernier Calipers consists of two scales of which one is fixed and the other is movable. The former is known as the main scale and the latter is the movable scale. The main problem with the earlier methods was the inaccuracy due to the differences in the length of the wrist or angul in their respective methods and hence the accuracy was very less. For better accuracy, the two important factors i. e. units and calibrations of the measuring instruments were developed. Instrumentation engineering plays a major role in the field of calibration, and it is needed for the instrument accuracy maintenance [8].

3.2 Measurements of Mass and Weight in the Vedic Period

In India, ratti, masha, chattank, tola, maund, and seer are some of the essential units of mass measurements. Ratti has a mass of 120mg (approx.) & it's a red seed that was frequently used by Goldsmiths and by the practitioners of the traditional medicine system in India. At the time of the pre-Akbar period, the weights system was varied from region to region, rural to urban areas, and commodity to commodity. The weights were based on the various seeds' weights which were made up of iron or stone shown in Fig.2. For weighing different quantities, balance (Tula) with two pans of differently sized were used. A grain of wheat or Barleycorn was the unit used for weighing the costly metals like gold and silver in the earlier stage which is later replaced by the larger units such as stone standards for the mass measurement [10]. The emperor Akbar standardized weights using a Barleycorn (Jau).

Fig.2: Weight Measurement technique in the Vedic period [10]

The following nomenclatures had been regularly occurring in North India before 1833 till the metric system came in [7]:-

- i. chawal (grain of rice) = 1 dhan (weight of one wheat berry)
- ii. dhan=1 ratti= 1.75grains=0.11339825 gram
- iii. 8 ratti = 1 masha = 0. 9071856 gram
- iv. 12 masha = 96 ratti = 1 tola =180 grains =11. 66375 gram
- v. 80 tolas = 1 seer = 870. 89816 gram
- vi. 40 seers = 1 maund = 8 pasri = 37.32422 kg
- vii. 1 chattank = 4 kancha = 5 tola
- viii. 1 pav = 2 adh-pav = 4 chattank = ¼ seer
- ix. 1 seer=4 pav=16chattank=80 tola=933.1 gms
- x. 1 paseri = 5 seer

The weight of wheat berries was used by the British as a standard. British chose Barleycorn to weight gold as the same as Akbar. The British made an effort to achieve uniformity in weights and measures. British rulers want to relate the Indian weights to those existing in Great Britain. In May 1833, the Government of India passed Regulation-VII of 1833, according to which the Farrukkabad rupee was altered to 180 grains in consonance with the Madras and Bombay rupee. The weight of this rupee was taken to be one "tola" which was a well- known native denomination and defined to be equal to 180 grains. Because of the adoption of these mass measurements, the Indian system was completely fallen on the British system. At last, a self-owned measuring system was introduced by the British for weighing gold (troy ounce), commodities (pound/cwt/ton) [11].

- I. One troy ounce = 480 barleycorn
- II. 1 troy ounce = 120 carat = 31. 1034768 gram
- III. 1 troy pound = 12 troy ounces.
- IV. Weight of 1 Barley corn= 64. 79891 milligram
- V. Weight of 1 Wheatberry = 45. 561732 milligram
- VI. Weight of 64 dhan (wheat Berries) = weight of 45 jau (Barley Corns)

In 1878, the troy Pound was abolished. In 1939 central legislature passed the standards of Weight act (Act IX of 1939) applicable to the whole of British and India. Once again it laid down a standard tola of 180 grains, 1 seer of 80 tolas, a maund of 40 seers, a pound of 7000 grains, an ounce equal to 1/16th part of a pound, a half hundred-weight of 112 pounds and a ton of 22 pounds. Thus, it allows creating a co-existence between the tola /seer/maund system with the pound /ton system. In 1956, the Government of India defined the standards of Weights and Measures Act (No. 89 of 1956, amended 1960, 1964) for metric conversion which was as follows:

- i. 1 seer =0.99910 kilogram = 80 tola=933.10 g
- ii. 1 maund = 40 seer = 37. 324 kg
- iii. 1 tola= 11. 66375 gram =12 masha
- iv. 1 masha = 8 ratti = 0. 97gram

3.3 Time Measurement in the Vedic period

The Indian time measurement system is considered to be one of the oldest time measurement

systems in the world. In ancient India, by observing the length of the shadow of the trees or other objects, the approximate time of the day was calculated. The lunar cycle was used to express the long-time durations. This is a very accurate, unique, and very précised measurement system. In this time measurement system, the measurement of time is based on the time rotation or revolution of various astronomical objects or heavenly bodies such as sun or moon.

It is known that there exist 12 months and each of the months consisting of 2 paksh (14 days) as per the orbiting of the moon around the earth. But there may be a slight variation in the actual number of days in a month as per the position of the moon and the sun. Another time unit is Paramanu which is measured from the largest possible notion of a Maha Yuga to the smallest measurable unit. During the Vedic period (5000 BC), the details of time calculation has been described in the Vedas and Manusmriti. India Vedic measurement system had separate names for much smaller time intervals [12]. The details of the terms for the smallest time interval and its multiples are described below:

Table-1: Different Time Units in the ancient period [12]

NAME	DEFINITION	EQUIVALENCE
Paramānu (atom)		26. 3μs (microsecond)
Anu	2 Paramanu	52. 67 μs (microsecond)
Trasarenu	3 Anu	158 μs
Truti	3 Trasarenu	474 μs
Vedha	100 Truti	47. 4 ms
Lava	3 Vedha	0. 1s
Nimesha (blink of an eye)	3 Lava	0. 43s (seconds)
Kshanas	3 Nimesha	1. 28 s (seconds)
Kāsthās	5 Kshanas	6. 4s (seconds)
Laghu	15 Kāsthās	1.6 minute
Nādika	15 Laghu	24 minutes
Danda		24 minutes
Muhurta	2 Danda	
Yāma	7.5 Muhūrta	
day(light)	4 praharas or 4 yamas	
Night	8 yamas = 1	
Day	day(light) + 1 night	
Paksha	15 days	Fortnight
Maasa	2 Paksha	Month
Ayanam	6 Maasa	6 Months

For a larger unit of time, the year is taken as the unit and has the following multiples:

1. 1 kaliyuga = 4, 32,000 human years
2. 2 kali yugas = 1dwaparyuga=864000 human years
3. 3 kali yugas = 1 tretayuga =1296000 human years
4. kali yugas = 1 satyayuga = 728000 human years

5. 10 kaliyugas = 1 mahayuga = 4,320, 000, human years
6. 1000 mahayuga = 1 kalpa = 4,320, 000,000 human years = 1 day of Brahma

The time interval second was originally the time of earth's rotation about its own axis. The time of rotation can be described as follows.

3.3.1 Seven Days of Week

All the Indians should be very happy to know that Veda is a very costly gift to this world. Earlier, it was discussed that, one day and night or ahorātra consists of 60 ghaṭis or daṇḍas. Each ghaṭi of the day was dedicated to a planet as its lord by the Indian astronomers. Again, the name of the day was decided as per the lord of the first ghaṭi of the day [11].

Table-2: Name of the day as per the planet

Ghati of The Day	Name of The Day
Surya	Sunday
Soma	Monday
Mangala	Tuesday
Budha	Wednesday
Guru	Thursday
Shukra	Friday
Sani	Saturday
Rahu & Ketu	Eclipse

The giver and sustainer of life is sun or Ravi and is a source of enormous energy which makes him the most powerful among the planet. This is why Sun is honoured as the lord of the first ghati of the first day of the week and hence named as Ravivara or Sunday. It may be concluded surely that the Vedic astronomers named a 7 days of a week using the Vedic measurement system by dividing one day and one night into 60 parts called ghaṭis and as per their succeeding attempt, they have shown that anyone can arrive at the same results using 24 hours as well. Again, planets' name is decided as per the order of weekdays written in the verse (1/296) of Yajnavalkya Samhita and so it can be strongly and easily believe that those planets' name in that verse was mentioned particularly as the lords of the 7 days of a week [13].

3.4 Measurement of Color in the Vedic period (Vedic concept for VIBGYOR)

Rig Veda says the light is a source of energy or source of all living organisms' life. Till late into the modern age, the nature of light was not coming into the picture as a wave or as a particle. But it was already mentioned in the Rig Veda that "Seven horses draw the chariot of the sun, tied by snakes" (Rig-Veda-5.45.9). This poetic verse delivers the knowledge about the nature of the light is the composition of 7 rays and its curved path is symbolized by the horses (Fig.3). These colors are described as red, orange, yellow, green, blue, indigo, and violet as per the yoga sutras and the Vedic Upanishads.

Fig.3: 7 horses represent 7 colours of sunlight (white light) [14]

These colours were not discovered in western science until 1666 which is when the splitting of light into its 7 colours by a prism experiment performed by Newton.

3.5 Measurement of Speed of light according to Rig-Veda

Velocity of Light was calculated by Maxwell in the 19th century but Speed of Light was determined accurately in Rig Veda thousands of years ago. It was further elaborated by Sayana in 14th century AD. The fourth verse of the Rig-Vedic hymn 1:50 (50th hymn in book of Rig-Veda) is as follows:

तरणिविश्वदर्शतो जयोतिष्कृदसि सूर्य | विश्वमा भासिरोचनम | taraNir vishvadarshato jyotishkrdasi surya | vishvamaa bhaasirochanam ||

It means “Swift and all beautiful art thou, O Surya (Surya=Sun), maker of the light, Illuming the entire radiant realm” [14].

Fig.4: Light traveling from Sun towards other planets with known speed [15]

Sayana who was a minister in the court of Bukka of the great Vijayanagar Empire of Karnataka in South India (in early 14th century) in his Rigvedic interpretation; commenting on this verse that:

“tatha ca smaryate yojananam. sahasre dve dve sate dve ca yojane ekena nimishardhena kramaman” [16].

It means “It is remembered here that Sun (light) traverses 2,202 yojanas in half a nimisha”

3.5.1 Proof for speed of the light which is written in Rig Veda and comparing with modern science

In the Vedas Yojana is a unit of distance and Nimisha is a unit of time (Nimisharda= half of a nimisha).

Unit of Time (Nimesa): The Moksha dharma parva of Shanti Parva in Mahabharata describes Nimisha as follows:

- i. 15 Nimisha = 1 Kashtra
- ii. 30 Kashta = 1 Kala
- iii. 30.3 Kala = 1 Muhurta
- iv. 30 Muhurtas = 1 Diva-Ratri (Day-Night)

It is known that the total day-night is 24 hours. Hence 24 hours = 30*30.3* 30* 15 nimisha which in total will be 409050 nimisha

Again, 1 hour = 60*60= 3600 Sec. So 24 hours = 24*3600 seconds = 409050 nimisha=86,400

seconds. 1 nimesa = 0.2112 seconds (This is a recursive decimal! Wink of an eye=.2112 seconds!),
 $1/2\text{nimesa}=0.1056\text{seconds}$.

Unit of Distance (Yojana): Yojana is defined in Chapter 6 of Book 1 of the ancient vedic text “Vishnu Purana” as follows [10]

- 1) 10 ParamAnus = 1 Parasúkshma
- 2) 10 Parasúkshmas = 1 Trasarenu
- 3) 10 Trasarenu = 1 Mahírajas (particle of dust)
- 4) 10 Mahírajas = 1 Bálágra (hair’s point)
- 5) 10 Bálágra = 1 Likhsha
- 6) 10 Likhsha = 1 Yuka
- 7) 10 Yukas = 1 Yavodara (heart of barley)
- 8) 10 Yavodaras = 1 Yava (barley grain of middle size)
- 9) 10 Yava = 1 Angula (1.89cm or appr. 3/4inch)
- 10) 6 fingers = 1 Pada (the breadth of it)
- 11) 2 Padas = 1 Vitasti (span)
- 12) 2 Vitasti = 1 Hasta (cubit)
- 13) 4 Hastas = a Dhanu, a Danda, or pauruSa (a man’s height), or 2 Nárikás = 6 feet
- 14) 2000 Dhanus = 1 Gavyuti (distance to which a cow’s call/lowing can be heard) = 12000 feet
- 15) 4 Gavyutis = 1 Yojana = 9.09 miles

Calculation: So now, the value of the speed of light in modern units can be calculated as follows: 2202 yojanas in $1/2$ nimesa = 2202×9.09 miles per 0.1056 seconds = 20016.18 miles per 0.1056 seconds = **189547 miles per second!! That is as per the Rig Veda.**

As per the modern science **speed of light given by Maxwell is 186000 miles per second!** [13]. Hence, there is the slightest difference between the two values to our error in accurately translating from Vedic units to SI/CGS units.

3.6 Distance Between Earth And Sun (Mention in Hanuman Chalisa)

There is a shloka written in Hanuman Chalisa as:

“Yug sahasra yojana par bhanu,
 leelyo taahi madhura phal jaanu”

The above shloka means to: When Hanuman travelled thousands of kilometers to swallow Sun thinking of it as a fruit (Fig. 5)

Fig.5: Lord Bal Hanuman is traveling towards the sun [12]

The word-to-word translation of the same shloka reveals the distance that Hanuman travelled. 1 Yuga = 12000 years. 1 Sahsra Yuga = 12000000 years. Also, 1 Yojan = 8 miles.

Hence in “Yug Sahasra Yojana”, the first 3 words mean $12000000 \times 8 = 96000000$ miles (1 mile = 1.6 km) or 153,600,000 kilometers. Interestingly, the actual distance from the earth to the sun is 152,000,000 km, bafflingly, there's an error of just around 1%.

4. MODERN SYSTEM OF UNITS FOR MEASUREMENT

In the course of the development of units, several systems were adopted. Two systems which were extensively used were the CGS and MKS system. The CGS system was based on centimetre, gram, and second as the unit of length, mass, and time while the MKS system used meter, kilogram, and second for the same. The International System of Units (SI) was adopted by the 11th General Conference on Weights and Measures (CGPM) in 1960. In the International System, there is only one SI unit for each physical quantity.

4.1 Meter for Length Measurement

The standard unit of length is meter, and was realized by employing stabilized Helium-Neon laser as a source of light. The metre is defined in International System of Units (SI) as the length of the path travelled by monochromatic light in a vacuum in $1/299\,792\,458$ of a second. [8].

4.2 Kilogram for weight measurement

Kilogram, having a unit symbol of kg is the fundamental unit of mass measurement in the metric system. It is defined as the mass of a particular international prototype made up of platinum-iridium and kept at the International Bureau of Weights and Measures. It was originally defined as the mass of one litre (10^{-3} cubic meter) of the pure water [8].

4.3 Second for time measurement

In 1967, the second was defined to take advantage of high precision attainable in a device known as an atomic clock, which uses the characteristic frequency of the caesium-133 atoms as the reference clock. But now, the second is defined (SI Unit for time) as the duration of 9192631770 periods of the radiation corresponding to the transition between two hyperfine levels of the ground state of the cesium-133 atom [8].

5. CORRELATION OF VEDIC TIME INSTRUMENTS WITH MODERN TIME ELECTRONIC BASED INSTRUMENTS

Many instruments which are widely used now in this modern time, had already been invented and used during Vedic time in so many ways either directly or indirectly. Some major instruments have been discussed below in a short and précised manner.

5.1 Electronics-Based Instruments

Invention of Portable Battery, Electric Dry cell, (The Concept of Electroplating): Rishi Agastya wrote a book named Agastya Samhita that describes the strategy of creating an electrical battery. He explained that water is split into oxygen and hydrogen. The battery cell resembles Agastya's methodology of generating electricity [17]. He was the primary Dry cell inventor which generates D.C current, hence he was also creditable for electricity generation [18].

5.2 Electrical Energy in Veda

In Veda, the electricity is mentioned by the name Indra and Vidyuta. Except this, Atharvaveda (2.5.12) refers to 2 sorts of electricity i.e. positive and negative along with its friendly and damaging nature. According to Ayurveda (1.16.5), the electricity is hidden within the water and once it comes out; it spreads light and provides energy. Ayurveda (1.85.5; 188.1) describes the use of electricity in weapons and telegraphy [19]. Electricity can be generated from energy as stated in Rig veda.1.45.5.

5.3 Digital Electronics in Veda

Veda gave us the knowledge of the existence of the whole universe from shunya. Brahmagupta is a scholar and mathematician in AD 628 who first time defined zero written as “Shunya” [17]. Later, Aryabhata who was a great mathematician discovered zero, and number system. It is now well-known that the whole digital electronics is based on zero and one.

5.4 Nuclear Instrumentation in Veda

Vedas gives knowledge about very powerful instruments like Brahmastra and Pashupatastra which is equivalent to the atomic bomb (Nuclear Energy source), discussed in Ramayana & Mahabharata [21].

5.5 Biomedical Instrumentation in the Vedic Period

Sushruta: The Father of Surgery (6th century BC) is a surgeon and the author of the book Sushruta Samhita. In that book, he has described over 120 surgical instruments, 300 surgical procedures, and has classified human surgery in 8 different categories [20].

5.6 Telecommunication-Based Instruments in Veda

Many Vedic scriptures tell us that saints in ancient times was attained a “siddhi” which means they could communicate to the people at a far distance and this was known as telepathy. Today, we have cell phones and internets to do the work which relates that we have achieved what was mentioned in Vedas [17].

5.7 Data Transmission Concept

Modern technocrats are dealing with wired or wireless data transmission. Wi-Fi connectivity, Bluetooth, growth in satellite connectivity is some emerging trends of the modern IT world in data transmission. The Lord Narada like Rishi and Yogi possessed some special powers of data transmission through the regular recitation of Mantra [17].

5.8 Dual Mode Signal Generator or Receptor in the Veda

The sending/receiving message by Sanjay in Mahabharata war set directly linked through satellites and these satellites were focused on the battlefield of Kurukshetra. The modern technology equipment firstly focused on the activity area and generates the signal with the help of satellite connectivity, or through the auto generator mechanism. Then it is sending the signals back to the same device which acts as a receiver of the signal. In the live audio and visual format, this same phenomenon was occurring in Kurukshetra which is mentioned in Mahabharata. That means Sanjay was working as a dual-mode signal Generator or receptor.

5.9 Embedded System in Veda: (Chitragupta– The supercomputer with high microprocessor)

In Rig Veda's text, lord Chitragupta is taken into account to stay meticulous, complete, and correct records of the actions of all groups of people from their birth until the death.

5.10 Artificial Intelligence, Robotics in Veda

In the 12th century "Samararingana sutradhara" discussed Yantra purusha (machine man), who was just like a human being who existed in the early era. Yoga Vasistha described the application of Artificial Intelligence (A.I) human emotions, ego to (Yantra purusha) Robots. Sambarasura created 3 robots using his technologies and named them dama, vyala, and kata [21].

5.11 Flight Instrumentation in the Vedic period

Vaimanika Shastra, which was written in Vedic time, had become a part of the Rig Veda. This is a Shastra, where before 7000 years; work had already been done by Maharshi Bharadwaj on the science of aircraft technology (Tripura Vimana, Rukma Vimana, Sundara Viman, Shakuna Vimana) [17].

6. CONCLUSION

Going through a comparative analysis of the Vedic measurement system (instrument, process, and standard) with the modern measurement system, it can be concluded that there is a significant relationship between these two measurement systems. Both the techniques are best in their respective times. The working principle of different measurement tools and instruments used in ancient times is very much related to modern time which shows that the Vedic period of India leads the world in terms of technology. The prime concern of our Rishis and Munis in the Vedic period was to protect the environment, atmosphere, and all living beings. It can be seen that, in that Vedic period, guru (teacher) prohibited their students from using any such types of instruments, and weapons which might be harmful for nature and all living beings. If some instruments like Brahmastra and Pashupatastra were having side effects on nature, then it was used very rarely, or even not used unless some emergency arose. It shows that Indian Rishis and Munis believe in

Om Sarve Bhavantu Sukhinah
Sarve Santu Niraamayaah |
Sarve Bhadraanni Pashyantu
Maa Kashcid-Duhkha-Bhaag-Bhavet |
Om Shaantih Shaantih Shaantih ||

Om, May All be Happy,
May All be Free from Illness.
May All See what is Auspicious,
May no one Suffer.
Om Peace, Peace, Peace.

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